

Conventional and point-of-care diagnostic tools for dengue virus detection and their possible treatments

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Abstract: Dengue fever is a mosquito-borne disease caused by infection with one of four dengue virus serotypes (DENV-1 to DENV-4) that causes significant morbidity, mortality, and economic costs, especially in developing nations. Dengue fever has surged 30-fold in the previous 50 years, and more than half of the world's population now lives in DENV-infected areas in more than 100 nations. There are currently a variety of traditional DENV testing methods available; including non-structural protein (NS1) based antigen testing, IgM/IgG antibody testing, and Polymerase Chain Reaction testing (PCR). New tools are also being developed that can save money and time. These tactics can be utilized in rural and low-income areas all around the world with great success. In this review, the virus's structural development is discussed before highlighting contemporary dengue detection strategies and the processes that are being developed or commercialized. The authors also critically reviewed the advanced bio-sensing devices and analyzed the sensitivity of these devices in detecting the DENV-infection. In the event of a repeat or future DENV outbreak, suggestions for enhanced diagnostic tool utilization have also been discussed. The last but not the least, a comprehensive summary of numerous old and recently developed therapeutics has been provided so that the researchers and clinicians may devise appropriate strategies for the timely and effective management of dengue fever.

Keywords: Dengue Virus; Traditional and POC diagnostics; Treatments; Non-structural protein

1. Introduction

Dengue fever is a viral infection spread by *Aedes* mosquitoes caused by four different dengue virus serotypes (DENV 1–4) (1, 2). As a result of increased geographical expansion, case numbers, and illness severity, dengue fever has evolved from a sporadic disease to a critical public health issue with considerable social and economic implications. Dengue fever is endemic in over 100 countries across Southeast Asia, the Americas, the western Pacific, Africa, and the eastern Mediterranean, and its prevalence has increased by 30 times in the last 50 years (3-6). DENV serotype 1 was the first DENV virus to be identified from human sera in Calcutta, India, in 1945(7). Fever, headache, nausea, vomiting, myalgia, arthralgia, rash, and leukopenia are among the most prevalent signs and symptoms of dengue fever (8, 9). Gingival bleeding, lethargy, hepatomegaly, hemoconcentration, thrombocytopenia, and fluid extravasation into bodily cavities resulting in ascites and/or pleural effusions are all symptoms of Dengue. DHF/DSS stands for Dengue Hemorrhagic Fever and Dengue Shock Syndrome, two conditions in which patients suffer plasma leakage, bleeding, respiratory distress, and visceral organ dysfunction, mainly in the liver and heart and central nervous system (10).

DENV is an enveloped, single-stranded, positive-sense RNA virus with a size of 11 kb (11). The RNA genome is around 10,700 nucleotides long and encodes a 3,411-amino-acid precursor polyprotein with three structural proteins, such as envelope proteins, precursor membrane proteins, or capsid [C] proteins. NS1, NS2A, NS2B, NS3, NS4A, NS4B, and NS5 are some of the non-structural proteins encoded by the viral genome (12-14). The structural proteins (which aren't involved in the replication of the viral DNA) are detected in mature virus particles, but the NS proteins (which are involved in the replication of the viral DNA) are found only in infected cells and are not packed into mature particles in detectable numbers (15). Through receptor-mediated endocytosis, DENV enters host cells. Viral attachment, endocytosis, uncoating, and fusion are all aided by the envelope proteins on the viral surface (16). Domain I (130–185), domain II (50–130, 185–300), and domain III (300–400) are the three functional domains of the envelope proteins (17). Domain II contains a fusion peptide, whereas domain III is a binding domain that interacts with cellular receptors and transports DENV particles to endosomal compartments in the host cell (18). In an acidic environment, viral uncoating occurs in

the cellular endosomal compartments, the cytoplasmic release of viral RNA. Even though it is a positive sense mRNA, protein translation begins as soon as the virus is uncoated. In the ER lumen and cytoplasm of the host cell, the genome RNA forms an unbroken polyprotein, which is then cleaved into individual proteins. PrM, E, NS1, and NS4B cleavage occurs before the other NS and C. For viral protein cleavage, host cell proteases and the viral protease NS2B-NS3 are necessary. In the cytoplasm near the cellular membranes, NS3 interacts with NS5, the RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RDRP), to facilitate viral RNA replication in so-called viral replication complexes (RCs) (19). Newly synthesized E and PrM inserted into the endoplasmic reticulum membrane on the cytosolic side, whereas newly synthesized RNA binds with capsid to create nucleocapsid on the ER membrane on the cytosolic side. Budding occurs when nucleocapsids interact with membrane-bound PrM and E to form progeny viral particles in the rough ER cisternae. These viral particles are transported to the Golgi apparatus, where they are secretory vesicles that carry them to the cell surface for extracellular release (20). A Golgi-localized furin protease cleaves precursor membrane proteins at a final stage of replication, resulting in M protein in the mature progeny virion discharged extracellularly (Figure 1) (11).

Dengue fever is spread through the bite of infected female mosquitos of the *Aedes* genus, especially *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* (21-23). Blood transfusions, organ transplantation, needle stick injuries, and mucosal spills are all examples of non-vector transmission. Unlike Zika, dengue illness has not yet to be related to sexual transmission (24). However, single-case research published recently revealed that dengue virus shedding in the sperm was protracted. When a woman is viraemic during the moment of delivery, vertical transmission is common. Transplacental transmission from illnesses that begin earlier in the pregnancy is not thought to occur, but official data are missing. Dengue virus was examined in 75% of 12 infected breastfeeding women, implying that transmission via breastfeeding is possible, despite the fact that no instances have been documented (25). Immature Langerhans cells and keratinocytes become infected with DENV after being bitten by the carrier insect *Aedes aegypti*. Infected cells are then transported to lymph nodes, where macrophages are activated. The infection then spreads to the bone marrow, liver, and spleen and, among other organs. DENV-induced bone marrow necrosis can cause hematopoiesis to be

Figure 1: The life cycle of the DENV is depicted in this diagram

suppressed, in addition to impaired blood thrombogenesis. The inflammatory response driven by chemokine and cytokine release by mast cells, macrophages, and lymphocytes leads to increased vascular permeability, platelet inability, thrombocytopenia, and plasma leakage (26). Although the mechanism is unknown, this cascade leads to enhanced spontaneous bleeding, resulting in petechiae, gingival bleeding, and gastrointestinal hemorrhage (27, 28).

Dengue infection differs from other febrile infections in that pathognomonic symptoms are less well known. As a result, it's crucial to identify this virus early (29). For its detection, different conventional approaches

such as virus isolation in cell culture, PRNT assay, serological assays, and molecular techniques are now used (30-32). However, they can't identify it in its early phases because culture takes several days, and isolation requires more equipment. On the other side, conventional procedures require the utilization of specialized or costly tools and are time-consuming (33).

Biosensors with analytical probes or biorecognition elements such as nucleic acid, immunoglobulins, antibodies, lectins, glycoproteins, and viral particles were utilized in the sensing system for quick, sensitive, and selective detection of the dengue virus. Because of the limitations of traditional diagnosis, biosensors have become more popular in recent decades

(34, 35). Dengue fever currently has no particular antiviral treatments or cures (36, 37). Dengue-related diseases can be treated with various drugs, such as acetaminophen, an analgesic, and antipyretic. Aspirin and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory medications (NSAIDs) are commonly used. Several anti-dengue medicines, notably carbazochrome sodium sulfonate (38), brefeldin (39), ketotifen (40), oral prednisolone as an anti-inflammatory agent, and lovastatin (41) have been studied in various clinical trials but more to be needed to manage the disease.

2. Dengue virus diagnosis using traditional methods

For adequate patient care and infection prevention, early and accurate DENV infection identification during the acute phase of the disease is crucial (42). Several traditional approaches to DENV diagnoses have been approved in a clinical setting, including viral isolation, immunoassays, and biochemical testing employing nucleotide probes (43). DENV RNA and antigens may no longer be detectable during early infection (5 days after infection), as the only viremia has ceased and antibody responses have risen. Specific antibody identification by serological methods (detection of IgM or IgG) is appropriate at this point (44). The NS1 antigen can be present in certain people for several days after they have defervescence. Because of their high sensitivities and specificities, both reverse transcriptase (RT)-PCR and real-time PCR procedures have been widely utilized in laboratory diagnosis (45).

2.1. Virus Isolation

Virus isolation is extremely precise and can help confirm a dengue virus infection. By inoculating clinical specimens into mammalian cell lines like Vero (African green monkey kidney), LLCMK2 (Monkey Rhesus kidney), and mosquito cell lines like C6/36 (*Aedes albopictus*) (46) and BHK21 (baby hamster kidney), DENV can be obtained (47, 48). Some of the clinical specimens utilized for virus isolation include homogenized tissue (most often in fatal cases), serum, whole blood, and plasma. Following inoculation and an incubation time, a confirmation assay, such as an immunofluorescence assay or a reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR), is needed (49). Virus isolation has significant practical drawbacks, despite its great specificity: (a) It's time-consuming, taking approximately seven days to incubate and validate

the results; (b) It necessitates the utilization of well-established lab facilities as well as well-trained personnel; (c) Only during the acute phase of infection is an opportunity for collecting samples available, and (d) Virus culture requires a high degree of DENV viremia (50).

2.2. PRNT

Another way to identify antibodies is with a plaque reduction neutralization test (PRNT) (51). In order to start the investigation, cells in a tube or plate are semi-solid medium covered to inhibit their progeny. A specified quantity of virus is mixed with a serially diluted serum sample (52, 53). Over the next few days, plaques will form and can be counted by the dying process, allowing plaques to be monitored. The plaques are then compared to see how much the overall virus's infectivity has decreased in relation to the virus's concentration (54, 55). This test evaluates DENV-preventive neutralizing antibodies, allowing for a more precise distinction between DENV antibodies and additional flaviviruses that cross-react with antibodies (56), despite being cross-reactive with other DENV serotypes (57, 58). On the other hand, this test is time-consuming, tedious, and has a low throughput (59-61). For these reasons, the PRNT isn't employed in regular diagnostics. A new generation of PRNT assays, such as an enzyme-based immunosorbent spot-microneutralization test and an ELISA-based microneutralizing test, has been developed to bypass these limitations (62).

2.3. Serological Tests

Because of their low cost and convenience of use, serological tests are the most widely used to detect dengue infection as compared to molecular or culture-based testing. The most common specimens used to detect the presence of IgM and neutralizing antibodies are serum and cerebrospinal fluid. On the other hand, plasma and whole blood samples are sometimes used as testing specimens. The existence of an IgG antibody could be used as a biomarker for diagnosing dengue fever. After an early infection, IgG levels stay high in people. It can result in ambiguous results for secondary infections and false positives in those who have been infected with or immunized against other flaviviruses such as yellow fever virus, West Nile virus, or Zika virus (63, 64).

In developing countries, serological assays for detecting IgM and IgG, such as the ELISA and hemagglutination inhibition (HI) assay, are more commonly used to diagnose dengue fever because they are simple to perform, relatively inexpensive, and the specimens required are stable at room temperature.

2.3.1. Hemagglutination inhibition: The E protein's ability to agglutinate red blood cells is used in the HI test (RBCs). This assay determines how effective anti-DENV antibodies in the blood are at preventing agglutination. Some limitations of this test render them undesirable, For example:

- Each subtype requires a different RBC pH, necessitating the use of multiple pH buffers.
- It can't differentiate between DENV and other Flaviviruses, or between immunoglobulin isotypes (IgM vs. IgG).
- Pretreatment with chemicals and heat may be necessary to remove nonspecific inhibitors from clinical specimens.

As a result, ELISA-based techniques for identifying dengue-specific IgM and IgG have almost completely replaced this assay (65, 66). ELISA is a biochemical method for detecting antibodies and antigens in a sample (67). There are two types of ELISA that are routinely used. Monoclonal antibodies are employed in a sandwich ELISA to identify the presence of target antigens in a sample, followed by enzyme-labeled antibodies that attach to a target antigen (68, 69). The indirect ELISA, on the alternative, uses immobilized antigens to see if there are any target antibodies in the sample, followed by target antibody binding to enzyme-labeled antibodies (70). After the immune complexes have been formed in both forms, the enzyme-substrate is added, and the enzyme substrate's subsequent reaction alters the color of the solution, indicating a positive ELISA test (71-73).

2.3.2. Immunoglobulin M-antibody captures ELISA (MAC-ELISA)

It's the world's most popular serological test. It's a sandwich ELISA method to detect dengue-specific immunoglobulin M (IgM), which appears five days after symptoms begin and lasts 30-60 days (74). Antibodies specific to IgM are mounted on a microplate to collect the total IgM in a serum sample. The dengue virus is then added, which binds to the IgM that has been captured. Immunological complex formation is identified utilizing enzyme-coupled monoclonal or polyclonal

antibodies that convert a colorless substrate into a colored result that can be measured using a spectrophotometer. This procedure is concise, precise, and quick, and it only necessitates the use of basic equipment (75). In the MAC-ELISA test, a single serum or matched sera from the patient can be used(76). The patient's positive diagnosis based on one serum sample implies that they are likely to have dengue fever. Although MAC-ELISA with a single serum sample may not ensure that a patient has dengue fever, the short processing time allows for immediate classification of suspected patients, which is particularly useful during epidemics. The time the sample was examined has a big impact on the sensitivity of this method. If the test was performed too early or on older or immune-compromised patients, the level of IgM might be below the detection limit (77). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that MAC-ELISA tests performed on a single acute-phase blood sample produce far more false negatives than false positives (63). Because of antibody cross-reactivity, the MAC-ELISA can't tell the difference between dengue serotypes (78, 79).

2.3.3. IgG ELISA: An immunoglobulin G (IgG) ELISA, similar to the MAC-ELISA, can be designed to detect current dengue infection utilizing the indirect approach (80, 81). Dengue-specific immunoglobulin G (IgG) appears seven days after the commencement of the fever and can last months or years. Because IgG is still detectable in the sick person, it has an advantage over MAC-ELISA in that it can detect previous infections. Primary and secondary infections can thus be distinguished using IgG and IgM capture ELISA to determine both IgG and IgM simultaneously (82). An IgM/IgG ratio greater than 1.2 or 1.4 (using a 1/100 or 1/20 dilution of the patient's serum) indicates an initial infection, while a ratio less than this figure indicates a secondary infection (83).

2.3.4. NS1 ELISA: A sandwich ELISA detection technique for the nonstructural protein 1 (NS1) has also been used to confirm cases of dengue disease (84). From the commencement of sickness to 12 days after onset, NS1 proteins might be found in patient blood serum in the range of 50 micrograms per milliliter (85). If the RT-PCR test for viral RNA is negative, but IgM antibodies are present in the blood sample, it can be identified after the viremia phase has passed (86, 87). So as a consequence, using NS1 as a marker of DENV infection offers a distinct advantage over other serological approaches, which have also demonstrated strong selectivity for other flaviviruses. Alternatively, NS1

Table 1: Different conventional methods for diagnosing dengue virus and its benefits and drawbacks (Cite in text)

S. No.	Methods	Advantages	Disadvantages
Dengue virus diagnosis using traditional methods			
1.	Virus Isolation	Confirmatory test, specific, identifies serotypes, more sensitive in comparisons to ELISA	Advanced and complex equipment and technological expertise are required, manpower and delivering result in a much longer period of time (106).
2.	PRNT	Measures, antibodies that neutralize DENV and prevent infection, allowing for a more precise distinction between DENV antibodies and other <i>flavivirus</i> antibodies.	This approach was found to have cross-reactivity with other DENV serotypes, Lab intensive technique, has low throughput and is time consuming (56).
Serological Tests			
3.	Hemagglutination inhibition	Dengue is more typically identified using IgM and IgG in underdeveloped nations.	The optimum pH of RBCs varies by serotype, demanding the use of several pH buffers, It can't tell the difference between DENV and other <i>flaviviruses</i> , or between immunoglobulin isotypes (IgM vs. IgG), and it could need chemical or thermal pre-treatment to get rid of nonspecific inhibitors in clinical samples(107).
4.	ELISA (MAC-ELISA, IgG ELISA, NS1 ELISA, etc.	Easy to perform, fast (results in 4-6 hours), less expensive, primitive equipment set-up.	The sensitivity of this approach is frequently affected by the time the sample was tested, False-positive due to cross-reactivity (108).
Molecular diagnosis			
5.	RT-PCR: Real-time RT-PCR, NASBA, RT-LAMP, etc.	Highly sensitive (80-90%) and specific (>95%), ability to determine dengue serotypes	Expensive, skilled person required, takes much time in comparison to serological assays (24-48 hours), the need of distinct storage temperatures.

detection is unable to differentiate among dengue serotypes at this time (88). This ELISA is useful for confirming DENV infection in serum samples taken 1–10 days after illness onset (89).

2.4. Molecular diagnosis

DENV infection has been effectively diagnosed using molecular techniques such as RT-PCR (qRT-PCR) and nucleic acid hybridization (90).

2.4.1. RT-PCR: The approach works on the idea of converting DENV RNA to cDNA utilizing reverse transcriptase enzymes. PCR amplification of the cDNA is then performed. It would be regarded as a positive outcome if a given nucleotide sequence was successfully amplified using a specific primer (91). This approach was further improved into a single-step multiplex real-time RT-PCR assay, which was widely accepted (92, 93).

PCR-based approaches have the benefit of being able to recognize RNA from viruses during the beginning of the disease and are more sensitive, specific, rapid, cost-effective, and less difficult to use compared to virus isolation methods. PCR-based techniques are quick and exact, but they require the use of a laboratory with specialized equipment and trained workers to complete the analysis (94). Furthermore, due to the inherent vulnerability of the dengue RNA genome, serum samples for RT-PCR experiments must be held at extremely low temperatures, which is not possible in many endemic areas (95, 96).

2.4.2. Reverse transcription-loop-mediated isothermal amplification (RT-LAMP) assay: The amplification process will be completed in thirty minutes under isothermal conditions at 65°C, making this assay relatively quick and straightforward (97). The buffer, primers, reverse transcriptase, and DNA polymerase are all mixed together in a single tube in this test.

Figure 2: Biosensors and their components are depicted graphically

The mixture should be incubated for 1 hour at 63°C. It has the advantages of reaction simplicity, high sensitivity, ease of use, and a shorter diagnostic time than RT-PCR and real-time PCR. It can amplify up to 10⁹ copies in less than 1 hour at isothermal circumstances (65°C) (98), but it has some drawbacks, including its high cost, the need for particular storage temperatures, the short time between collection and extraction, and its usefulness in very early phases of sickness (about five days) (99). The NASBA method of isothermal amplification is another widely utilized technology (100, 101). This test has the advantage of being a single-step isothermal technique that targets DENV RNA (102, 103).

RNA is extracted from clinical serum or plasma samples using silica, which is subsequently amplified at 41 degrees Celsius without the use of a thermocycler (50). The amplification can be finished in less than 30 minutes, and the output can be detected via electrochemiluminescence (63). DENV detection tests based on NASBA have been published in a couple of publications (104). NASBA also has several drawbacks, such as the following:

- I. NASBA is most concerned about RNA integrity, like RT-PCR and other RNA amplification techniques.
- II. Although the amplification reaction is isothermal at 41°C, annealing of the primers to the target necessitates a single melting step prior to the amplification reaction.
- III. Furthermore, because thermolabile enzymes are required for reaction specificity, the reaction temperature cannot exceed 42°C without harming the process.
- IV. Finally, the target sequence for amplified RNA should be between 120 and 250 nucleotides in length, with shorter or longer sequences working poorly (105).

3. Recent diagnosis techniques of DENV

Biosensors can be considered as a more sophisticated diagnostic tool, with high sensitivity, specificity, low volume, and user friendly (109-112). Biology and electronics are combined to make the system more accessible, digital and to develop a multiplexed strategy on a tiny scale (113, 114). As a matter of fact, combining the two areas benefits the healthcare system greatly. In addition, recent advances in nanotechnology and their implementations in the biomedical field have resulted in the foundation of novel approaches in medical

diagnostics, health surveillance, food security, and other fields (115, 116). The unique and adaptable features of nanoparticles have caught the interest of a diverse research community with diverse interests. Nanomaterials can improve electrical device performance while also lowering limits of detection and increasing sensitivity (117, 118). Antibodies, DNA, antigens, and aptamers are a number of recognition elements used in biosensors (119, 120). Biosensors are categorized as genosensors (when nucleic acids are used), immunosensors (when antibodies and antigens are used), and aptasensors (when aptamers are employed) on the basis of biological recognition molecules (121, 122). However, further work is expected to get them commercialized as quickly as conceivable. However, the biosensor's core concept is given in diagram form in Fig. 2 (115). Biosensors are categorized into the following groups based on molecular recognition, for example:

3.1. Genosensor

The Genosensor, also known as a gene-based biosensor, employs the immobilization of DNA samples as a detection element, and various binding strategies, including the creation of DNA-RNA, DNA-DNA combinations, and the interconnections among proteins and DNA ligands edge of the device, were investigated (123). The creation of triplex DNA (Hoogsteen/Hoogsteen reverse hydrogen bonding) and DNA hybridization (Watson or Crick base pairing) are both responsive sequence and wide gene sequence variants (124, 125). DNA biosensors (genosensors) for clinical diagnostics and forensic analysis have sparked a lot of interest (126). Genosensor is therefore utilized to identify DENV. Figure 3 illustrates the operation of a genosensor for DENV detection. Researchers like electrochemical genosensors because they are simple to make and have a quick response time. The most commonly used electrochemical techniques are cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance technique (127).

The recently published study showed a multiplexed electrochemical paper-based analytical device (ePAD) made of graphene oxide-silicon dioxide (GO-SiO₂) nano-composites that could identify a specific Dengue virus strain (DENV). The genosensor's signal response was amplified due to the conducting nature of the GO-SiO₂coated multiplexed platform. The target DNA of the four dengue virus serotypes, DENV1, DENV2, DENV3, and DENV4, was identified in a

detection range of 100 pM to 1mM using the present sensor (128). Rahman et al. demonstrated a highly effective molecular electronic-based detection using silicon nanowire (SiNW) combined with a typical complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) process as a sensing device for detecting DENV-related deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) in an early stage diagnostic. The immobilization of probe DNA and their hybridization with target DNA are sensed by monitoring variations in the current of SiNW, which bridge the source and drain terminal. By modifying the SiNW surface, oxygen (O₂) plasma has been offered as a viable technique for enhancing target DNA binding quantities. The optimized O₂ plasma-treated SiNW device's detection limit was decreased to 1.985×10^{-14} M with the sequence-specific DNA's detection range from 1.0×10^{-9} M to 1.0×10^{-13} M (129).

DNA reporter probe, dengue-1 target RNA, and a dengue-1 specific DNA capture probe mounted on a nitrocellulose membrane. On the LFB strip, a positive test resulted in a red test line, allowing visual detection. The enhanced biosensor has a cut-off value of 0.01 μM with the use of synthetic dengue-1 as a target. The dengue-1 virus was detected in pooled human sera with a cut-off value of 1.2×10^4 pfu/mL in a proof-of-concept use of the biosensor (130). By improving the stable system between cadmium selenide tellurium sulfide fluorescent quantum dots (CdSeTeS QDs) and gold nanoparticles (AuNPs), the development and validation of a quick and quantitative DENV serotype-specific (serotypes 1–4) biosensor is reported in a published paper. Each primer-probe serotype-specific hairpin single-stranded DNA covalently attached at different places to CdSeTeS QDs is used to create four distinct

Figure 3: Genosensor and their operating function are displayed

New research demonstrated a colorimetric lateral flow biosensor (LFB) for visual detection of dengue-1 RNA using dextrin-capped gold nanoparticles (AuNP) as a label. The detection was made using nucleic acid sandwich-type hybridization between an AuNP-labeled

nanoprobes, each of which produces a different fluorescence signal for each DENV serotype. Standard dilutions of the target virus DNA from 10^{-15} to 10^{-10} M were successfully identified in fourplex reactions using free functionalized AuNPs and the four nanoprobes. The

synthetic ssDNAs of DENVs 1, 2, 3, and 4 were shown to have detection limits in the femtomolar range, with values of 24.6, 11.4, 39.8, and 39.7 fM, respectively (131).

A silicon nanowire biosensor with innovative molecular gate control for Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) detection linked to the dengue virus has been demonstrated in this research. The silicon nanowire was created by combining electron beam lithography (EBL), plasma dry etching, and size reduction methods to nanostructure silicon-on-insulator (SOI) layers. A three-step approach that involved surface modification, DNA immobilization, and hybridization was used to functionalize the surface of the produced silicon nanowire. This approach serves as a molecular gate control for establishing electrical detection for DENV DNA oligomer 27-mers base targets. The silicon nanowire biosensors were found to have a sensitivity of $45.0 \mu\text{A M}^{-1}$, indicating that the sensor can detect DNA across a wide range. The achieved LOD was around 2.0 fM (132). A Zinc oxide/platinum-palladium-modified electrochemical genosensor (ZnO/Pt-Pd) was manufactured to detect the consensus DNA sequence of the dengue (DENV) virus using methylene blue (MB) as an intercalating agent. Probe DNA (PDNA) was immobilized on the surface of a modified FTO electrode made from ZnO/Pt-Pd nanocomposites. This PDNA modified electrode (PDNA/ZnO/Pt-Pd/FTO) was used as a signal amplification platform for the detection of hybridized DNA targets (TDNA). The interaction of an anionic mediator, methylene blue (MB), with free guanine (3'G) of ssDNA, led to a lower current, which was used to detect hybridization between PDNA and TDNA. The sensor's dynamic linear range was $1 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$ to $100 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$, with LOD of $4.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ and LOQ of $9.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ (133).

The creation of an electrochemical DNA biosensor for the detection of dengue virus (DENV-3) serotype 3 sequences has been reported by Oliveira et al. Using bioinformatics software, a DENV-3 probe was created. A 22-m sequence was shown to be the most effective DNA probe for detecting DENV-3. The optimal concentration of DNA probe fixed on the electrode surface is 500 nM, and the device has a low detection limit (3.09 nM) (134). A new class of brilliant, luminous CdSe/ZnSeS core/alloyed shell quantum dots (Qdots) with size-dependent functionalized glutathione (GSH) has been produced. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were conjugated to Qdots to generate AuNP-Qdot nanohybrids in the initial step of the biosensor design.

The AuNP-Qdot nanohybrids were then conjugated to the 5' end of the MB in the second process. Despite their strong binding, the AuNP-Qdot and AuNP-Qdot-MB conjugates were highly colloidal stable. DENV1–4 nucleic acids were identified with great sensitivity by AuNP Qdot-MB biosensors, with detection limits ranging from 31–260 copies/mL for the serotypes. The biosensor was able to distinguish between each viral serotype (135). A new class of nanocomposite comprising gold nanoparticles (AuNP) and nitrogen, sulphur codoped graphene quantum dots (N,S-GQDs) was used in a study to present a two-way detection approach for Dengue virus (DENV) serotype identification and DNA quantification. The results show that the N,S-GQDs@AuNP can detect the four DENV serotypes separately in the concentration range of 10^{-14} to 10^{-6} M with a LOD of 9.4 fM in this investigation (136).

A new and robust method was discovered by employing a disposable screen-printed gold electrode (SPGE) that used silicon nanowires (SiNWs) and gold nanoparticles as sensing material to detect DNA oligomers related to the dengue virus. SiNWs/AuNPs-SPGE was first created by dispersing SiNWs in 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES, 0.5%) onto naked SPGE. Second, by a self-assembly monolayer (SAM) process, the AuNPs coating on the SiNWs-SPGE surface was functionalized with dithiopropionic acid (DTPA). After hybridization on SiNWs/AuNPs-SPGE, the electrochemical response of methylene blue (MB) as a redox indicator to synthetic DNA oligomer was measured. The results showed that the MB reduction peak current was considerably decreased following the DNA hybridization process. Furthermore, the proposed biosensor demonstrated good storage stability, with a linear range of 1.0×10^{-11} – $1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ ($R= 0.98$) and a detection limit of $1.63 \times 10^{-12} \text{ M}$ (137). The detection of dengue virus serotype 2 (DEN-2) using a reflectance spectrophotometric approach was achieved using an optical genosensor based on Schiff base complex (Zn²⁺-salphen) DNA label and acrylic microspheres (AMs) as polymer support of the capturing DNA probe (cpDNA). The reflectometric DNA microsensor had a wide linear detection range for DENV-2 DNA, ranging from $1 \times 10^{-15} \text{ M}$ to $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, with a low limit of detection (LOD) of $1.21 \times 10^{-16} \text{ M}$ (138). Tripathy et al. developed an ultrasensitive electrochemical platform for DNA hybridization detection based on electrospun semi-conducting Manganese (III) Oxide (Mn₂O₃) nanofibers. The suggested technology combines the

inherent benefits of metal-oxide nanofibers with electrochemical transduction techniques to produce label-free zeptomolar DNA hybridization detection. The results show zeptomolar detection of Dengue consensus primer in both control and spiked serum samples as proof of concept (limit of detection: 120×10^{-21} M) (139).

A recently paper presented an EIS-based genosensor for the label-free and nucleic acid amplification-free detection of isolated DENV RNA for a sensitive diagnosis of DENV infection. To modify thin-film gold electrodes as a link to control the coverage of self-designed probe DNA (pDNA) at a density of $4.5 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{11}$ pDNA/cm², a concentration ratio of 0.04 mM 6-mercaptophexanoic acid (MHA) to 1 mM 6-mercapto-1-hexanol (MCH) was chosen. Compared to previous MHA/MCH ratio-modified genosensors, the pDNA/MHA/MCH-modified genosensors have been shown to improve the hybridization efficiency of a synthetic 160-mer target DNA (160mtDNA) with a 140-mer electrode side overhang. The MHA(0.04 mM)/MCH(1 mM)-modified genosensors show good hybridization efficiency with DENV serotype 1 (DENV1) RNA samples, with the same electrode side overhangs as the 160mtDNA, with a low detection limit of 20 plaque-forming units (PFU)/mL, a linear range of 102–105 PFU/mL, and good selectivity for DENV1 (140). Based on a novel square-planar piperidine side chain-functionalized N, N0 -bis-4-(hydroxysalicylidene)-phenylenediamine-nickel(II) that could intercalate via nucleobase stacking within DNA and be functionalized as an optical DNA hybridization marker, a sensitive and selective optical DNA biosensor for dengue virus detection has been developed. 3-Aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTS) modified pore silica nanospheres (PSiNs) is produced utilizing a simple mini-emulsion procedure to function as a high-capacity DNA carrier matrix for this purpose. The Schiff base salphen complexes-labeled probes used to detect nucleic acid on PSiNs causes the DNA biosensor to become yellow, which can be measured using a reflectance transduction approach. The reflectometric DNA biosensor showed a broad linear response range to target DNA within the concentration range of 1.0×10^{-16} – 1.0×10^{-10} M ($R_2 = 0.9879$), with an ultralow limit of detection (LOD) of 0.2 micro-M. With a reaction time of 90 minutes, the optical DNA biosensor response remained constant and maintainable at 92.8 percent of its initial value for up to seven days of storage (141).

A relatively newly developed technique utilizes a clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR) system with methylene blue (MB)-conjugated Au nanoparticles (MB-AuNPs) to produce a highly sensitive electrochemical biosensor for the detection of DENV. The CRISPR/Cpf1 (CRISPR from the *Prevotella* and *Francisella* 1) system, which consists of CRISPR RNA (crRNA) and Cpf1 enzyme protein, detects a target sequence and randomly cleaves a nonspecific single-strand DNA (ssDNA) with targeted DNA. Without using any RNA amplification procedures, the created electrochemical biosensor was able to detect DENV-4 at a low concentration of 100 Fm (142). The sandwich hybridization technique of DNAs on succinimide-functionalized poly (n-butyl acrylate) (poly (nBA-NAS) microspheres was used to develop a DNA micro-optode for dengue virus detection. A centrifugation-based process was used to make gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) with an average diameter of 20 nm, which were then electrostatically adsorbed on submicrometer sized polyelectrolyte-coated poly (styrene-co-acrylic acid) (PSA) latex particles. Au-thiol binding was used to link the AuNP-latex spheres to the thiolated reporter probe (rDNA), resulting in an optical gold-latex-rDNA label. A pair of DNA probes, namely capture probe (pDNA) and AuNP-PSA reporter label flanked the target DNA (complementary DNA (cDNA) in the one-step sandwich hybridization recognition. The concentration of dengue virus cDNA was optically transduced by immobilized AuNP-PSA-rDNA conjugates, as the DNA micro-optode exhibited a violet hue following the DNA sandwich hybridization procedure, which could be measured using a fiber-optic reflectance spectrophotometer at 637 nm. The optical genosensor demonstrated a linear reflectance response throughout a large cDNA concentration range 1.0×10^{-21} M to 1.0×10^{-12} M cDNA ($R_2 = 0.9807$) with a limit of detection (LOD) of 1×10^{-29} M (143). Self-assembly was used to create a composite of 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (APTES) functionalized graphene oxide (APTES-GO) wrapped around SiO₂ particles (SiO₂@APTES-GO). When compared to both APTES-GO and APTES-SiO₂ electrode materials, the SiO₂@APTES-GO electrode material displayed improved dengue RNA detection sensitivity, selectivity, and detection limit (1 femtomolar) (144).

The traditional photolithography process was used to construct a poly-Si nanowire biosensor in this research. This method is also used to define the initial poly-Si with a 1µm dimension. After going through the

traditional photolithography procedure, the photoresist was developed with a resist developer and etched with reactive ion etching (RIE). While the nanowire was hybridized with dengue DNA type-2 (DENV-2) at concentrations ranging from 10fM-10 μ M, an increase in current was observed (145). Odeh et al. describe a real-time amperometric DNA detection system for the dengue virus. Cu₂CdSnS₄ (CCTS) quaternary alloy nanostructures were effectively produced, spin-coated onto an oxygen-etched silicon substrate (O₂/Si), and annealed at 400 degrees Celsius. A thermal evaporator vacuum coater and a hard mask were used to manufacture interdigitated electrodes with silver as a metal contact placed on the CCTS/O₂/Si substrate. The quaternary alloy supports the immobilization of the recognition element, which is a Dengue-specific DNA probe. Amperometry was used to recognize single-stranded DNA at concentrations ranging from 100fM to 10nM, with an average working voltage of 1.5 V. 17 nM is the lower detection limit. 24.2 μ A nM⁻¹ cm⁻² is found to be the sensitivity (146). Based on a carbon nanotube network coated with gold nano-particles, electrical pulse biasing was employed to selectively and sensitively detect a target DNA sequence in serum, i.e., dengue fever virus-specific sequence in this study. In the serum, the approach was able to detect target DNA molecules with a large dynamic range (10 pM-10 μ M). In the detection of target DNA molecules in serum, it was shown that a detection limit as low as pM concentration could be obtained (147).

A new class of bright luminous CdSe/ZnSeS core/alloyed shell quantum dots (Qdots) with size-dependent glutathione (GSH) functionalization has been produced and analyzed. Gold nanoparticles (AuNPs) were conjugated to Qdots to create AuNP-Qdot nanohybrids in the initial step of the biosensor design. The AuNP-Qdot nanohybrids were then conjugated to the 5' end of the MB in the next step. Despite their strong binding, the AuNP-Qdot and AuNP-Qdot-MB conjugates have excellent colloidal stability. DENV1-4 nucleic acids were identified with remarkable sensitivity by the AuNP-Qdot-MB biosensors, with detection limits ranging from 31-260 copies/mL for the serotypes. Each virus serotype was distinguished by the biosensor (135). By improving the stable system between cadmium selenide tellurium sulfide fluorescent quantum dots (CdSeTeS QDs) and gold nanoparticles, the development and validation of a quick and quantitative DENV serotype-specific (serotypes 1-4) biosensor is reported in this paper. Each primer-probe serotype-

specific hairpin single-stranded DNA covalently attached at different places to CdSeTeS QDs is used to create four distinct nanoprobe, each of which produces a different fluorescence signal for each DENV serotype. Standard dilutions of the target virus DNA from 10⁻¹⁵ to 10⁻¹⁰ M were successfully identified in fourplex reactions using free functionalized AuNPs and the four nanoprobe. For all four serotypes, the femtomolar limit of detection was determined (131). An integrated electrochemical biosensor based on an aluminum nanoparticle doped zinc oxide nanostructure has been devised and developed for the diagnosis of the dengue virus. Interdigitated electrode (IDE) is developed with Ag (silver) and integrated on Si-AZO by utilizing a hard mask and thermal evaporator systems (PVD). The constructed (IDE (Ag)/AZO/Si) platform is functionalized by DNA immobilization, hybridization, and surface modification to set up electrical detection for a dengue-specific DNA probe in concentrations of 100fM, 100pM, and 10nM. Wide range detection reached a sensitivity of 55.54A nM⁻¹ cm⁻², limit detection 15.46A nM⁻¹, and limit quantification 51.53A nM⁻¹ (148).

3.2. Immunosensor

Immunosensors are built on the interaction of antigen-antibody (149, 150). The biological recognition component in this approach is either an antibody or an antigen. Antibodies are unique and delicate to toxins, infections, and other substances (151-153). Immunosensors are often known as biosensors since they contain biological components such as antibodies (154, 155). This antibody delivers the sensor's selectivity and sensitivity. The antigen interacts antibody with a high affinity, enabling it to recognize the analyte even when other chemicals are present (156). In most cases, this material is immobilized into a second components transducer, responsible for converting a biophysical or biological event into an electrical signal. The antibody attaches to the analyte and is digitalized or amplified by an electrical component (157). Figure 1 is a diagrammatic representation of an immunosensor. The immunosensors have been categorized as electrochemical immunosensors, optical immunosensors, and piezoelectric immunosensors on the basis of transducer technology (158). On the basis of immunoassay, they can be direct, in which case the immunochemical reaction is determined by analyzing physical changes induced by complex development, or indirect, in which case the joining of detectable labels

occurs when antigen or antibody complex formation occurs. Non-labeled immunosensors have high selectivity, although non-specific adsorption on the bio-recognition surface is still a difficult task for direct techniques (159). However, the immunoassay approach has one important drawback: cross-reactivity with other *flaviviruses*. However, it also includes a number of advantages; as a result, it is a better diagnostic platform. The following are the essential steps in immunosensor preparation: (a) optimal immobilization strategy that

detecting, classifying, and screening antibodies for DENV. The authors observed that the type and quantity of viruses exposed on the surface influenced the charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) of a gold electrode coated with graphene oxide reinforced polymer. This observation was explained using the molecular recognition capabilities developed during the creation of the GO-polymer composite. R_{ct} was linearly related to viral concentrations in the range of 1 to 2×10^3 pfu/mL 17 DENV, with a

Figure 4: Diagram showing components of Immunosensor and their functions

allows antibodies to bind in the correct orientation;(b) optimum antibody surface density; (c) large surface area; and (d) choosing the best matrix for antibody immobilization (for example nanostructures) (160).

Based on electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, this work proposes a new method for

detection limit of 0.12pfu/mL (161). Dengue virus detection was proposed using a label-free electrochemical immunosensor. The circulating DENV NS1 antigen was detected in both spiked and infected samples using modified polyaniline (PANI) coated Glassy Carbon (GC) electrode immobilized with DENV

NS1 antibody. 0.33 ng.mL⁻¹ was found to be the Lower Limit of Detection (LOD) (162). Lim et al. employed polyvalent phage display to find specific affinity peptides for the NS1 protein. These strategies were used to select a prospective affinity peptide-displayed phage. Its sequence was EHDRMHAYLTR (R3 # 10). According to amino acid sequence analysis, the peptide had many basic residues (two His and Arg). R3#10 had the largest decrease in CV current and increased EIS impedance after binding to NS1 proteins of all the evaluated peptides. In comparison to bovine serum albumin or the M13 wild type employed as a control, EIS demonstrated that R3#10 phage clones were more specific for NS1 proteins. 0.025 µg/mL was reported to be the detection limit for peptide-displayed phage that had not been altered (R3#10) (163). Kumar et al. described a new lateral flow immunoassay for the detection of dengue fever that takes advantage of the features of gold-coated graphene oxide sheets as detection labels and a tapered nitrocellulose membrane.

The newly designed assay enables the quick (10 min) and sensitive detection of dengue NS1 with a 4.9 ng/mL detection limit, an improvement of approximately 11-fold over previously reported values (164). Zainuddin et al. describe a prototype device for an integrated electrochemical and mass-sensor for dengue NS1 antigen and preliminary validation investigations. The sensor is easily portable because it is coupled with OpenQCM, an open-source mass-sensing software, and hardware. The sensitivity of the sensor is improved by having dual measuring capabilities (mass and impedance). According to preliminary research, the prototype might reach ultralow limits of detection as low as 10 ng/mL, dual-sensing cross-validation, portable size, sample-to-analysis time of less than 30 minutes, and parallelization of several assays (165). The current study shows methods to construct a nonstructural antibody (NS1)-based immunosensor with a BSA-modified screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) as a transducing substrate for early dengue virus identification. On the electro grafted BSA surface of the working electrode, the anti-NS1 monoclonal antibody was immobilized. The electron transfer resistance was measured before and after NS1 attachment as a function of its concentration to conduct the qualitative and quantitative study. With an improved limit of detection (0.3ng/mL) and linear range (1-200ng/mL), the impedimetric immunosensor successfully detected the dengue viral protein (166). The creation of microfluidic paper-based analytical devices (PADs) based on a sandwich immunoassay on wax

patterned paper functionalized with anti-dengue NS1 monoclonal antibodies for dengue NS1 (DEN-NS1-PAD) point-of-care detection is described here. Various test parameters were optimized, including channel length and diluent, and the reaction was recognized by the naked eye and digital images within 20–30 minutes. In the field, the DEN-NS1-PAD successfully detected dengue NS1 in buffer, cell culture media, and human serum. The DEN-NS1- PAD's limit of detection (LoD) was 200, 46.7, and 74.8 ng/mL, respectively, when measured with the naked eye, scanner, and smartphone camera (167). An effective electrochemical biosensor for detecting dengue virus NS1 was established in this study, which utilizes chemically modified affinity peptides. A number of synthetic peptides with different amino acid substitutions were rationally designed, chemically produced, and covalently attached on a gold sensor surface. The dynamic current drop in SWV tests led to the selection of potential affinity peptides specific for NS1. The molar ellipticity of peptides (DGV BP1–BP5) was evaluated using circular dichroism, demonstrating that they were mainly comparable in random coil structure but not completely identical. DGV BP1 was chosen as a promising recognition peptide using SWV, and the 3-sigma rule revealed that the limit of detection for NS1 was 1.49 g/mL. DGV BP1 demonstrated excellence and stability in NS1 (168).

Wasik et al. described a low-cost, label-free, ultra-sensitive, and quick detection of the entire dengue virus using an electronic biosensor based on a single-walled carbon nanotube network chemi-resistive transducer functionalized with heparin. For the first time, heparin, a derivative of the heparan sulfate proteoglycans that act as dengue virus receptors in Vero cells and hepatocytes, was employed as a biorecognition element in a biosensor instead of a conventional antibody. For both humans and infected *Aedes aegypti*, the biosensor showed sensitivity in the clinically relevant range. For DENV suspended in PB, a limit of detection of 8.4×10² TCID₅₀/mL (~8 DENV/chip) was achieved after only ten minutes of incubation of a 10 µL sample(169). In recent years, researchers have begun to use a surface plasmon resonance (SPR) optical sensor to diagnose the dengue virus (DENV). A spin coating approach was used to create an immobilized monoclonal antibody (IgM) on a gold/Fe-MPA-NCC-CTAB/EDC-NHS thin film. When IgM immobilized gold/Fe-MPA-NCC-CTAB/EDC-NHS thin film is exposed to DENV E-protein solution at concentrations ranging from 0.0001 nM to 10 nM–1, the SPR signal can be measured, and

DENV E-protein detected. It was revealed that there is a linear relationship between SPR angle shift and DENV E-protein concentration up to 0.01 nM, with a sensitivity of 39.96° nM⁻¹ (170).

3.3. Aptasensor

Aptamers are short nucleic acids that are obtained from very large combinatorial oligonucleotide libraries using an iterative in-vitro amplification and selection procedure (171). Systematic evolution of ligands by SELEX is the term of this selection strategy (exponential- enrichment) (172, 173). A random oligonucleotide library (usually 10¹⁵–10¹⁶) is used to begin the operation (174). Amplification, partition, binding, and elution are all steps in the SELEX process. The fundamental approach would be to develop a pool of oligonucleotide sequences. For polymerase chain reaction amplification, every nucleotide in this repository core randomized sequence of 20–80 nucleotides that is coupled by fixed-primer sites of 18–21 nucleotides. The target molecule is accustomed to incubating the library pool after it's created (175, 176). These few oligonucleotides in the library are referred to as aptamers because they can connect towards the target. Elution is the procedure for extracting the solution into unbound nucleic acids while simultaneously separating the bound target's nucleic acids. Finally, with the aid of the PCR, the binding oligonucleotides are amplified and could construct a novel library (149, 177). Aptasensors are much smaller, measuring 5–25kDa, and have greater selectivity and physicochemical stability besides comparing to antibody counterparts. Aptamers' cheap or batch variation, low vulnerability to denaturation, ease of modification to facilitate covalent-bonding for material surfaces, and long storage life are all appealing properties. These benefits have sparked new advancements in aptamer-based sensors, referred to as aptasensors. By means of signal transduction, which includes optical, electrical, mass-sensitive, and micromechanical sensing, it is possible to classify aptasensors (178, 179). Aptasensor immobilization technique; Aptamer bioreceptors can be bonded to a huge spectrum of surfaces in Aptasensors, including polymers, carbon nanotubes, and metals. Self-assembled monolayers, particular chemical contacts, electrostatic interactions, hydrophobic interactions, and covalent interactions are some of the surface immobilization techniques that have been proposed. Because the immobilization method utilized affects the detection

accuracy of biosensors, selecting the proper one is crucial. Gold (Au) is a common substrate for biosensors. The most common ways to immobilize aptamers on gold surfaces are through thiol-Au or amine-Au interactions (180). Aptamers are becoming more relevant in the field of molecular identification and therapy. Aptamers-based biosensors offer substantial benefits over biosensors that focus on biological receptor-like enzymes and antibodies. For example, aptamers that have a higher affinity &, in general, the specificity of aptamers-based bio-sensors can be tuned in vitro for a wide range of targets, ranging from small to big molecules, cells, and proteins, enabling for the development of bio-sensors with a wide range of applications. Second, once an aptamer has been selected, it may be made with greater reproducibility and clarity using commercially available materials (181-183).

The following are some of the benefits of using aptamers instead of antibodies or immunosensing for detection:

- A. Because aptamers are recognized in vitro (SELEX), selection parameters can be adjusted to keep aptamers stable in a variety of environments.
- B. Because aptamers are created through chemical synthesis, there are few to no differences across batches, and reporter molecules can be coupled to aptamers at appropriate places.
- C. Aptamers can be easily amplified and recognized because they are oligonucleotides. Aptamers that have become denatured can be recovered in minutes and preserved for longer periods of time (184).

However, because aptamers-based sensors are still not user-friendly for average operators, practical applications of Aptamers-based sensing and diagnostics are still lagging. According to current sources, colorimetric sensors that concentrate on signaling aptamers are a positive move toward enhancing user-friendliness since detection findings that are possible with the naked eye without the implementation of complex instruments are a positive step in the right direction (185). The goal of this research was to create a DNA aptamer-based electrochemical biosensor for NS1 detection. A self-assembled monolayer was obtained by immobilizing gold electrodes with particular aptamers and 6-mercapto-1-hexanol (MCH). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy and atomic force microscopy were used to characterize the platform and adjust the molar ratio between aptamers and MCH. In order to avoid non-specific interactions, bovine serum albumin

was added to the NS1 solution to stabilize and block the surface. The biosensor's performance was evaluated using NS1 protein serotype 4 (in phosphate saline buffer and human serum) as well as a serotype 1 solution in human serum. The results revealed a sensitivity of 2.9 percent, 2.7 percent, and 1.7 percent per decade, with low detection limits of 0.05, 0.022, and 0.025ng/mL, respectively. As a negative control, the platform was also tested with envelope protein (186).

Mok et al. proposed a novel G-quadruplex (GQ)-based fluorescent aptasensor that uses one-shot detection of NS1. A Dengue virus-derived NS1-binding aptamer (DBA) with a GQ structure was created to design the aptasensor. The authors wanted to use the DBA for optical sensing after it was structurally destroyed by nonstructural protein 1 (NS1). In order to find the NS1-dependent structural alteration, 6-carboxyfluorescein (FAM) was added to the 5' end of DBA (5' FAM-DBA). The fluorescence quenching generated by guanines upon NS1 binding could be detected quantitatively using the 5' FAM-DBA, making dengue disease diagnosis possible. The authors looked at the structural and fluorescence properties of the interaction between NS1 and DBA to learn more about it. The findings indicated that the core G-tracts had been rearranged to be next to the FAM, and that the structure of 5' FAM-DBA bound to NS1 should create base-pairing. Low detection limits of 2.51nM in buffer and 8.13nM in serum were reached using the aptasensors (187). According to Rashid et al., an electrochemical technique based on an NS1-specific aptamer and cationic polymer-induced aggregation of gold nanoparticles was used to detect the dengue virus. The core idea of this assay is based on the progressive aggregation of AuNPs, which is controlled by particular interactions between PEI (polyethyleneimine), aptamer, and NS1. The cationic polymer caused AuNP aggregation, which was controlled by the aptamer-cationic polymer interaction, generating a "duplex" structure. This non-specific contact between the aptamer and the polymer was expected to reduce the aptameric chain's flexibility, making the aptamer more accessible to the target molecule (NS1). Because of strong electrostatic interaction with the aptamer, this NS1 accession was responsible for the creation of quadruplexes. This cationic polymer and aptamer-assisted dispersion-aggregation phenomena result in a shift in electrochemical response, which could eventually be used to explore the sensitive detection of NS1 protein

with a limit of detection of 0.3ng/mL and a linear range of 3–160ng/mL (188).

4. Treatment options

There is yet no specific antiviral treatment or cure for the dengue virus (36, 37). The WHO's amended treatment guidelines emphasize two points: Fluid administration and symptomatic treatment. As an antipyretic and analgesic, acetaminophen is the only symptomatic treatment available. Aspirin and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are not suggested due to their antiplatelet activity, which might result in thrombocytopenia-related bleeding. Fluid administration is determined by the patient's condition. Oral administration is sufficient in moderate situations and whereas if an individual is able, though patients should be checked frequently (82, 189). Clinical studies have looked into a number of anti-dengue therapeutic medicines (which address host and viral components), such as carbazochrome sodium sulfonate for capillary leakage prevention (38) and brefeldin (produced by the fungus *Penicillium brefeldianum*) (39), ketotifen is a mast cell stabilizers and a non-competitive antihistamine (40). At the endothelium, oral prednisolone operates as an anti-inflammatory medication (41), while lovastatin (190) acts as an antiviral and anti-inflammatory.

In small-scale trials, single platelet donations (191) or recombinant human (rh) IL-11 (192) have been examined to reduce severe bleeding or reduce the time it takes for bleeding to stop. Other anti-DENV drugs like chloroquine (inhibits virus-host membrane fusion) (193, 194), sofosbuvir (DENV2 polymerase inhibitor) (195), celgosivir-glucosidase I inhibitor (196), and balapiravir-nucleoside analog and polymerase inhibitor have also been examined in clinical studies. Monoclonal antibodies, viral invasion or fusion inhibitors, replication and transcription, methyltransferase, helicase, protease (197), and an NS4B blocker have all been developed. There are various obstacles to overcome in developing this ultimate anti-dengue therapy (198-200). The method of management and therapy of DENV fever, researchers are currently researching and developing a huge spectrum of medicines. For example, the Sunitinib/erlotinib combo, for example, modifies inflammatory cytokine responses in DENV-infected mice (201), α -Mangostin fully blocked dengue serotypes 1 & 3 productions while significantly reducing serotypes 2 and 4 productions by 100 times. Furthermore, it has been shown to significantly inhibit the transcription of

chemokines such as RANTES, MIP-1 β , and IP-10, as well as cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 (202).

Luteolin, a flavonoid, inhibits the proprotein convertase furin, which limits DENV replication (203). TNF- α , IFN- γ , TGF- β 1, IL-4, IL-6, IL-12, and IL-17 were among the cytokines and interleukin parameters that were reduced by a recently established therapeutic miRNA approach, while several coagulants factors increased after treatment (204). Metadichol helped the two dengue fever patients with falling platelets recover from the sickness in just a few days (205). A synthetic flavonoid, ST081006, was demonstrated to be a strong inhibitor of DENV replication (206). Uncaria rhynchophylla's indole alkaloid Hirsutine was discovered as a strong anti-DENV compound with low cytotoxicity and great efficacy (207). Minocycline is an antibiotic that blocks the manifestation of intracellular envelope proteins, the production of RNA, and the formation of infectious virions within cells (208). Tomatidine- is a 3-beta-hydroxy steroid (antiviral properties) (209), Adefovir dipivoxil (an antiviral regimen that strongly attaches to the receptors of serotypes-1 and 2) (210).

Dengue treatments should have pan-serotype activity, relieve symptoms fast, be well tolerated with little toxicity, be easily distributable on a broad scale, have minimal drug interactions, and be safe for adults, children, babies, women who are pregnant, and those having co-morbidities. The process of developing this optimal anti-dengue therapy is challenging (198). It's been difficult to find an inhibitor that works against all four DENV serotypes, for example, because of the significant amino acid sequence diversity (30–35 percent) across these groups. Because producing antibodies that are equally protective against all serotypes is difficult, intravenous administration is favored (211). Furthermore, no real animal model resembles human DENV pathogenesis (212), which hinders progress toward a secure and efficient treatment.

5. Conclusions and Future Perspectives

Dengue fever is found in over 100 countries throughout Southeast Asia, the Americas, the western Pacific, Africa, and the eastern Mediterranean, and its frequency has increased by 30 times in the previous 50 years. Dengue infection symptoms include fever, headache, nausea, vomiting, myalgia, arthralgia, rash, and leukopenia. Plasma leakage, bleeding, respiratory distress, and visceral organ dysfunction, primarily in the liver, heart, and central nervous system, characterize

dengue Hemorrhagic Fever and Dengue Shock Syndrome (DHF/DSS). The current laboratory testing methods for detecting dengue virus infection and their therapy are compared in this study. The most direct route to dengue diagnosis was found to be virus isolation, RT-PCR, and serology approaches. On the other hand, these methods involve time-consuming procedures, high-cost requirements, and highly qualified personnel. Various biosensors were used in this study, including Genosensor, Immunosensor, and Aptasensor in detecting dengue fever have been described and compared. We also discussed the many DENV fever treatments that have recently been discovered. The future of testing could be crucial in terms of developing cheaper, sensitive, and quick examinations. One of the key difficulties that must be considered in the diagnostic formulation process is variation in serotypes and genomic sequences. Although developing a single confirming test can be difficult, it is necessary for optimal patient treatment. In the future, these research avenues should be investigated in order to provide simple and faster confirmatory tests. In rural places, where traditional examinations are unavailable, these types of testing can make a difference. Hybridization of diverse technologies, such as paper–hydrogel and paper–thread-based technologies, on the other hand, can be employed to improve diagnostic sensitivity and lower costs. None of these new products have yet been approved by the FDA for clinical use.

Commercialization of more POC-based assays should be prioritized since they can considerably improve disease surveillance, testing, and management. There is yet no specific antiviral treatment or cure for the dengue virus. Clinical studies have looked into a number of anti-dengue therapeutic medicines (which address host and viral components), such as carbazochrome sodium sulfonate for capillary leakage prevention and brefeldin (produced by the fungus *Penicillium brefeldianum*).

Ketotifen is a mast cell stabilizer and a non-competitive antihistamine. Oral prednisolone operates as an anti-inflammatory medication at the endothelium, while lovastatin acts as an antiviral and anti-inflammatory. Dengue treatments must have pan-serotype activity, relieve symptoms fast, be well tolerated with little toxicity, be easily distributable on a broad scale, have minimal drug interactions, and be safe for adults, children, babies, pregnant women, and patients with co-morbidities. It will be challenging to develop this optimum anti-dengue treatment. In

conclusion, a greater understanding of the host's innate and inflammatory pathways is required, as this knowledge can aid in the identification of relevant targets. Antiviral drugs targeting inflammation and endothelial barrier permeability could be developed without interfering with the host immune system if such inhibitors are targeted. Resolving the concerns raised in this paper can lead to a better understanding of DENV and related host variables, which can be used to identify novel therapeutic targets for anti-dengue medications.

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7. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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